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Integration of digital marketing strategy in community dentistry practice business model

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Abstract

Community dental practices require good entrepreneurial management to maintain the continuity of the practice in meeting patient needs more effectively in the competitive era of dentistry. One important aspect of dental entrepreneurship management is marketing strategy. Marketing strategies are carried out to increase service visibility, build patient trust, and expand the patient base. The purpose of the study was to analyze effective marketing strategies for dental practices with management and entrepreneurship. The research method uses a qualitative research design of literature study (library research) systematically from books, national and international journals such as Scholar, PubMed, Science Direct, Elsevier, Scopus, and others. As well as data sources obtained from other online articles through the Google search engine. The results of the research were obtained through study selection techniques using relevant keywords that management and entrepreneurship in dental practices are important with digital marketing strategies. Digital marketing strategies are carried out to increase the competitiveness of community dental practices. The first step of the marketing strategy is to analyze the market and find out the patient's needs. Then by utilizing the development of digital technology such as the use of websites, social media, advertising and branding and reputation. To increase the competitiveness of community dental practices in addition to implementing marketing strategies, of course, prioritizing excellence in service and human resources such as competent doctors to achieve patient satisfaction. The conclusion of the study is that entrepreneurial management through digital marketing strategies in community dental practices is important to achieve the business objectives of dental and oral health practices and help provide satisfactory services for patients related to oral health.

Keywords: Keyw Community dental practice; Digital marketing strategy; Dental management; Entrepreneurship

1. Introduction

The presence of community dentistry is very helpful for the community in maintaining dental health. The field of community dentistry contributes in the form of services to the community regarding the importance of dental health care such as the prevention of dental caries, health promotion, and the development of policies to promote oral health equality and improve access to public dental care services (Indriyasari, 2024). Dental health is an important aspect of life because dental health affects the health of the body as a whole. In the practice of community dentistry, it is just like a company that requires good management. The field of community dentistry also recognizes various types of management in accordance with the scope of activities and resources managed. Some of the necessary dental management such as personnel management (personnel management), finance, drug and equipment logistics, health services (dentists), management information systems, and so on. This management can be found in hospitals, health centers, dental practice clinics, and others (Agung, 2020).

Management in the field of community dentistry is very necessary in an era of increasingly sophisticated technological developments. This is due to the increasingly competitive practice of dentistry in the era of technological development

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such as the emergence of new tools that are increasingly sophisticated, increasingly competent health workers and several other supporting aspects in dentistry. In the world of community dentistry, not only clinical expertise and medical knowledge from a doctor are needed. But other factors such as tools that follow technological developments to help the success of a dental professional in providing the best care for patients. Dentists are not only faced with being competent practitioners but also reliable business managers who are able to provide the best service for their patients.

Management and entrepreneurship in dental practice are very important. This is because management and entrepreneurship play an important role in maintaining the continuity of the practice to meet patient needs more effectively. Especially to face the competitive world of dentistry in competition for patients (McMeen S, 2022). Management becomes a strategy to face competitiveness in medical practice. Dentists must have good management and entrepreneurship as a strategy to face other dental practice competitors. One important aspect of dental entrepreneurship management is marketing strategy. The success of marketing strategies in the competitive era of dentistry depends on developing a plan to achieve this success (McGuigan & Eishner, 2006).

Marketing strategies in community dental practices include a variety of approaches designed to increase service visibility, build patient trust, and ultimately expand the patient base. Marketing can help dental practices attract new patients, increase patient satisfaction, and strengthen the loyalty of existing patients. In addition, effective marketing helps dental practices face market competition and adapt to technological developments and consumer behavior trends in the digital era. Management and entrepreneurship in community dental practice strategies, dentists must know within themselves what distinguishes their own dental practice from other practices. Dentists must know the needs of prospective patients (Levin, 2007).

In the era of technological development, digital marketing strategies in community dental practices also play a key role to achieve the best results such as enabling the fulfillment of expectations and prioritizing the interests of product offerings to target more diverse patients. Digital marketing plays an important role in driving business in dentistry (Grieco, 2024). In this context, it is important for practitioners such as dentists to understand management and entrepreneurship as a marketing strategy effort in the community dentistry sector. This study aims to analyze effective marketing strategies for community dental practices with management and entrepreneurship. It is hoped that the research conducted can provide benefits from the business side, but also visibility, competitiveness of dental practices and improve the quality of health services for the community.

2. Material and methods

The research design is qualitative research using library research systematically. Data sources were obtained from books, national and international journals such as Scholar, PubMed, Science Direct, Elsevier, Scopus, and others. As well as data sources obtained from other online articles through the Google search engine. The inclusion criteria used were related to relevant keywords. Research is carried out based on checking, confirmation through research synthesis, namely by extracting themes and research concepts that are in accordance with the research direction. Then perform the organization of the results of the article extraction in key findings, create group categories from the research results, and synthesize categories based on the conceptual framework of the research.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Community Dentistry Management and Entrepreneurship

Management studies managing and organizing all things related to administration and others. Management can be used in everyday life, one of which is in community dentistry practice. In the scope of dentistry, management is related to dental and oral health services in order to provide optimal service to patients, it is necessary and rules in a good management process. Dental management is a reality for dental health workers to be able to understand management science properly and skillfully as well as a reference or foundation in providing dental and oral health services (Agung, 2020).

Not only management in dentistry, entrepreneurship in dental practice is increasingly important given the policy shift towards pseudo markets, competition, new contracts, and patient choice. Entrepreneurship provides a relevant role involving the process of starting a business venture, organizing the necessary resources, and assuming the associated risks and rewards. In dentistry, this process involves further practice development, practice amalgamation, or the start of a new practice. Entrepreneurship provides a framework of continuing competence as a development and assessment tool in the healthcare sector. The reason for this is the importance of the relationship between competence and

performance, the demographic, psychological and behavioral characteristics of entrepreneurs and their technical skills and knowledge are often cited as the most influential factors on performance (Willcocks, S., 2012).

In community dental practices, strong entrepreneurial management is necessary to enhance competitive strategies. Dentists will likely have multiple points in a career in dentistry. The choice is to start a new business or join a practice. Entrepreneurship and management training can help dentists to make and implement career decisions (Mollica, et al., 2017). During the career process, dentists will learn a lot of management and entrepreneurship that can increase patient visits. Here dentists must provide their role as personnel who provide the best service for patients. Dentists can provide information about the objectives of community dentistry which include dental caries prevention programs, health promotion, and services that will be obtained when performing dental treatment (Indriyasari, 2024). Attitudes, ways of service, and educational techniques related to oral health to patients are important to note. As much as possible, dentists provide informative and easy-to-understand explanations about problems and how to maintain oral health to patients. The first impression of the dentist for the patient is the key to attracting patients. Patients who get the best service will certainly conduct an examination or treatment at a clinic that provides the best service if they experience problems with their dental health. Even with good service, patients will give good word of mouth testimonials to those around them. This is the initial strategy in business in the field of community dental practice by providing management techniques through the best service.

Dentists are expected to develop the business objectives of their respective organizations. This is an area where dentists may have an advantage, given their experience in running a community dental practice as a business. The role may include setting goals or strategies relating to expansion, shrinkage, merger, or recovery. For example, dentists will be involved in identifying which services are most effective and cost-effective and planning new investments and divestments, using evidence and experience. It is suggested that there are four key factors that may be related to the development of an entrepreneurial role for dentists i.e. the characteristics of the individual entrepreneur, the sector of operation, the processes and resources used by the entrepreneur and the mission and outcomes associated with the entrepreneur. These four factors will be used as a way to conceptualize the entrepreneurial role in dental practice (Willcocks, S., 2012).

3.2. Digital Marketing Strategy Improves Competitiveness of Dental Practices

An important aspect of community dentistry management and entrepreneurship is digital marketing strategy. Marketing strategy as a technique to increase the competitiveness of community dental practices. In the era of digital technology development, the presence of websites and social media is an effort to market dental practices. Here are some marketing strategies for dental practices through digital technology.

3.2.1. Website

Website as a digital marketing strategy for community dental practices. The website must contain informative information related to dental practices and be easy to navigate. Because many people choose to search for information via smartphones by visiting websites. The website should be mobile-friendly and have a visually appealing design and provide logical navigation. Quality content can help dental clinics connect with new and existing patients about their oral health issues. In addition, the website can contain information in the form of articles related to oral health and some of the objectives of community dentistry such as dental caries prevention, oral health promotion, and oral health support. The presence of the website confirms the reputation of the dental clinic as a competent expert in the field of today's technological developments.

3.2.2. Social Media

A digital marketing strategy to increase the competitiveness of community dental practices is to use social media. Social media offers a good way to connect personally with patients. However, the competition is fierce. Marketing strategies through social media allow dental practices to stand out from the crowd. Social media engagement to share information about new things in the practice, how dentists and team members provide feedback to patients. Social media marketing strategies include Instagram stories and popular content formats that target location-based communities to make it easier to reach patients and potential patients in the practice area.

3.2.3. Online Advertising

The digital marketing strategy of community dental practices is through online advertising by utilizing search engines (SEM) and Search Engine Optimization (SEO). This involves extensive keyword research to determine what terms people use to search for dentistry services.

3.2.4. Branding and Reputation

Community dentistry clinic digital marketing strategy through branding and reputation. Reputation management plays an important role. Potential patients will pay close attention to what current patients have to say about the dental practice including the services provided. Reviews or testimonials from old patients influence a wider audience than just word of mouth to build a good reputation and branding to build public trust (S, MacMeen, 2022).

Branding of dental practices can be done with testimonials through google maps search reviews. Doctors can ask patients if they wish to provide google maps reviews or testimonials regarding the services provided.

3.3. Challenges in Marketing Community Dentistry Practices

Dental practice marketing certainly has its own challenges. To face the challenges in dental practice marketing, it is necessary to analyze the market, understand the needs and preferences of patients, and target the right patients. Specific challenges in dental practice marketing include maintaining the practice's competitive advantage in the context of financial constraints and increased competition, for example, from private dental companies. The role of entrepreneurs is to provide the impetus for organizational change, with entrepreneurs involved (Willcocks, S., 2012).

In marketing dental practices will certainly be faced with strict rules and regulations. Often marketing practices in medicine will cause conflicts such as conflict of interest conditions that violate medical ethics (Setiabudi, et al., 2020). Therefore, dentists in marketing strategies should not use excessive marketing tactics and misleading claims so that there are limits to promotion. Another major challenge in marketing dental practices is competition between clinics. To deal with this, branding needs to be done by the clinic. Branding to build a reputation by creating a unique marketing strategy and differentiating dental clinic services from competing clinics. Dental clinic marketing strategies have challenges in maintaining patient trust and loyalty. In this case it is necessary to manage good relationships with patients on an ongoing basis. Dental management can provide information and training to dentists on how to provide good customer service and ensure every patient feels comfortable and satisfied. It is important to build a reputation through patient satisfaction testimonials to build the trust of other potential patients.

3.4. Suggestions for Community Dentistry Practice

A community dental practice's digital marketing strategy can go through the initial step of thoroughly analyzing the components that influence the internal and external environment. This can be used to plan the marketing strategy. The current external environmental factors are changing rapidly which brings many opportunities and risks. Internal environmental factors are also changing, impacting strengths and weaknesses (Arifiya, et al., 2024). Marketing strategy in dentistry by analyzing the needs and preferences of patients. Usually patients have different needs, for example orthodontic treatment, cavity treatment, tartar, and so on.

It is important for dental clinic practices to know the services that are in demand by the surrounding community where the dental clinic is located. Another important factor that needs to be considered as supporting patients to come to the clinic is the comfort and quality of service because this is an important value to attract new patients to come to the medical practice clinic. Furthermore, the cost of dental health care is affordable. Many patients consider the cost of dental health care. Dental clinics can provide certain price packages that are attractive to patients. In addition, it is important to analyze marketing data and evaluate dental clinics by tracking the metrics of the number of patient appointments, the growth of positive reviews, and patient feedback on the services provided by dental clinic personnel. Prioritizing excellence in service and human resources from medical personnel, trained personnel, and striving to achieve patient satisfaction are important things to consider in dental practice management.

4. Conclusion

Entrepreneurial management through digital marketing strategies in community dental practices is important to achieve the business objectives of dental and oral health practices and help provide the best services related to oral health in the community in the current era of technological development. With a digital marketing strategy in community dental practices, it will not only attract patients to come to the clinic. Of course, it will help the clinic provide the best service to patients. Dental management and entrepreneurship are important to plan the right marketing strategy to improve the business of community dental practices. Some things that need to be done such as analyzing the needs and preferences of patients and prospective patients. Marketing of community dental practices can be through the utilization of technological developments such as websites, social media, advertising, building branding and enhancing a good reputation. In community dental practices, not only management and marketing strategies, but also the primacy of dentists in providing the best service to the community. Then the hope is that this research can be a

reference for further research on the importance of management and entrepreneurship in the community dental practice business.

References

- [1] Agung, I Gusti Ayu Ari. (2020). Module: Principles of Dentistry Management. Faculty of Dentistry Mahasaraswati University, Denpasar.
- [2] Grieco, Cecilia. (2024). Conceptualizing Inclusive Marketing: A Syntesis of Theory and Practice. European Management Journal.
- [3] Indriyasari, Arini. (2024). Literature Review: Behavioral testing of dental Caries Patients with a Community Dentistry Approach as an Effort to Promote Dental Health. Mandiri Cendekia Journal of Health Science. Vol 3(7) pg. 150-158.
- [4] Levin, Roger P. (2007). The Role of Branding in Dental Practice Marketing. The Journal of the American Dental Association. Vol 138(4) pg. 530-531.
- [5] Mc Guigan, Patrick J. (2006). Marketing The Dental Practice: Eight Steps Toward Success. The Journal of the American Dental Association. Vol 137(10) Pg. 1426-1433.
- [6] McMeen S (2022). Following Best Practices For Dental marketing. Dental Abstracts. Vol. 67(2) Pg. 91-92.
- [7] Mollica, Anthony G, Cain, Kevin, Callan, Richard S. (2017). Using Assesments of Dental Students' Entrepreurial Self-Efficacy to Aid Practice Management Education. Journal Dental Education. Vol 81(6) Pg.726-731.
- [8] Willcocks, S. (2012). The Entepreneurial Role in Primary Care Dentistry. British Dental Journal. Vol. 212, Pg. 213-217.